

An advanced global soil erodibility (K) assessment including the effects of saturated hydraulic conductivity

Surya Gupta^{a,*}, Pasquale Borrelli^{a,b}, Panos Panagos^c, Christine Alewell^a

^a Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Basel, Basel 4056, Switzerland

^b Department of Science, Roma Tre University, Rome, Italy

^c European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Ispra, Italy

HIGHLIGHTS

- A global K factor map was modified to consider soil hydraulic properties (Ksat).
- This modification reduced the K factor (K_{ksat} , 1 km) especially in tropical regions.
- The global K_{ksat} has refined spatial patterns catching more heterogeneity.
- Future work should improve the map with more Ksat data from data scarce regions.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

USLE-type models are widely used to estimate average annual soil loss at large scales, with the erodibility factor (K) being the sole component that accounts for soil's susceptibility to erosion. The factor includes the information on permeability in the equation, however, most definitions of the K factor consider the soil hydrological influence only very crudely and indirectly. Thus, the direct impact of surface runoff infiltration and drainage on soil erosion is largely neglected. The objective of this study is to incorporate soil hydraulic properties in the K factor map by merging available global-scale measured saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ksat) data with soil texture and organic carbon information into a modified K factor. To achieve this, the Wischmeier and Smith (1978) soil texture- and permeability-based equation ($K_{Wischmeier}$ factor) was modified to include Ksat, called K_{ksat} factor. Using the Random Forest machine learning algorithm, the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor and the K_{ksat} factor were each correlated with soil and remote sensing covariates for spatial extrapolation of two independent K factor maps at 1 km spatial resolution. We noted a clear decrease in the mean value of the K_{ksat} factor ($0.023 \text{ t ha h}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$) compared to the mean value of the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor ($0.027 \text{ t ha h}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$). The reduction in K_{ksat} factor values was most pronounced in tropical regions reflecting the difference in soil properties (e.g., clay and iron), whereas other climate regions showed relatively minor changes in comparison to the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor as well as to the recent global modeling of Borrelli et al. (2017) (K_{GloSEM} factor maps). As many studies discussed an overall overestimation of (R)USLE based erosion rates compared to measurements, this reduction in the K

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: surya.gupta@unibas.ch (S. Gupta).

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factor might improve modeled erosion rates in the right direction. The K_{ksat} marks an important initial step in integrating hydraulic properties into the K factor of USLE-type models and can prove their significance in future studies.

1. Introduction

Soil erosion is a crucial environmental process that can lead not only to soil degradation, reducing soil fertility, water retention capacity, and crop yield but even more so to the instability of whole ecosystems (Troeh et al., 2004; Pimentel and Burgess, 2013). To predict soil erosion, mathematical models have been used for several decades, which are classified as empirical, conceptual, or process-oriented models (Nearing, 2013; Bagarello et al., 2018). A systematic review of soil erosion models applied worldwide including a statistical analysis to identify knowledge gaps, identified the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) family of models as the most commonly used model globally for soil erosion prediction on small and large spatial scales (Rozos et al., 2013; Borrelli et al., 2021; Jin et al., 2021). Also, empirical or simple models were found to be not only more frequently but also more successfully used than process-based models (Borrelli et al., 2021) when defining successful modeling as yielding plausible results (e.g., compared to measured erosion rates, soil production or formation rates, and visible erosion features). Although the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) was originally deduced using an empirical-based procedure, Ferro (2010) demonstrated that its structure can be theoretically deduced and presented the logical structure with respect to the variables used to simulate the physical soil erosion process. Process-based models have several limitations, such as requiring more input data, which can contribute to increased input errors and model complexity (Boardman and Favis-Mortlock, 1998). Additionally, these models require a large amount of input data, but they do not guarantee better performance compared to empirical models (Favis-Mortlock, 1998; Morgan and Nearing, 2000; Alewell et al., 2019).

The empirical USLE-type models comprise six main input factors, including rainfall erosivity (R-factor), soil erodibility (K-factor), length and slope (LS-factor), cover crop (C-factor), and management practices (P-factor) (Valkanou et al., 2022). K is the factor that in the USLE-type equations describes the inherent susceptibility of soil to erosion, which is regulated by the structural/textural stability of soil aggregates (Qian et al., 2022). Numerous studies indicate that the K factor has a significant impact on the intensity of erosion and is commonly employed to estimate soil erosion rates throughout the erosion processes (Iaich et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2014). Since the K factor was developed based on a small number of soils in the United States, it is necessary for other contexts to check the K factor ability to predict the soil's true erodibility (Bagarello et al., 2012). There are already several K factors maps available at large scales. For example, Borrelli et al. (2017) and Yang et al. (2023) produced global K factor maps, Panagos et al. (2014) produced a K factor map for Europe, Riquetti et al. (2022) for South America, and Raj et al. (2023) for India. However, these maps only crudely and indirectly incorporate infiltration and drainage of surface runoff in soil erosion estimates through the use of soil texture, specifically rough soil texture-based permeability and structure classes. The inclusion of permeability classes based on soil texture for the K factor may overlook the impact of vegetation, biopores, clay minerals, and other factors (Or, 2020). As the USLE-type models were developed in the temperate regions, the latter might enhance the often-discussed bias of models and underlying scientific concepts towards temperate regions and the unsuitability of these models and concepts for, e.g., tropical regions. According to Hodnett and Tomasella (2002), there are differences in the types of clay minerals found in soil textures between temperate and tropical regions. In temperate regions, the dominant clay mineral is smectite (which consists of a 2:1 ratio of tetrahedral and octahedral layers), whereas in tropical regions, the dominant clay

mineral is kaolinite (which consists of a 1:1 ratio of tetrahedral and octahedral layers). As noted by Lehmann et al. (2021), the response of these two clay minerals to infiltration and hydraulic properties differs considerably. As infiltration and hydraulic properties have a direct influence on soil erosion (e.g., via runoff production and/or siltation), we assume that incorporating measurements of saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ksat) into the K factor might broaden the applicability of the model concept and enhance the accuracy of soil erosion estimations in non-temperate regions.

Ksat is a measure of water movement in and within the soil under saturated soil conditions. It differentiates the amount of water that infiltrates into the soil from the amount of water that flows over the surface as runoff (Dirksen, 2000; Bagarello et al., 2004). Various studies have emphasized the significance of Ksat information in soil erosion and surface runoff modeling. For instance, Flanagan and Nearing (1990) and Onsamrarn et al. (2020) discovered that Ksat is one of the most sensitive input parameters for predicting runoff. Jadczyzyn and Niedźwiecki (2004) revealed a strong negative correlation between Ksat and soil loss (indicating that soil loss decreases with an increase in Ksat). They found that Ksat and sand content accounted for 80 % of the variation in soil loss and concluded that Ksat could be utilized to evaluate soil erosion losses. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2010) demonstrated the importance of Ksat in comprehending the impact of soil erosion. They conducted a study in the Loess Plateau of China to examine surface runoff on newly formed dam farmlands using Ksat values. The results showed that higher Ksat values led to reduced surface runoff, while lower Ksat values resulted in higher surface runoff.

Several studies have demonstrated the relationship between Ksat and K factor with different soil properties in separate studies (Qian et al., 2022; Ostovari et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the connection between K factor values and Ksat values has not yet been explored. Therefore, our aim is to incorporate measured Ksat values, which represent soil hydraulic properties, into the Wischmeier and Smith (1978) soil texture-based K factor equation ($K_{Wischmeier}$ factor) in order to develop the Ksat-based soil erodibility (K_{ksat} factor) map. These values are collected from the literature and explained in the methodology section. Furthermore, we demonstrate the difference between $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor and K_{ksat} factor values based on point dataset calculations. Following that, we elucidate the model training process for producing $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor and K_{ksat} factor maps by utilizing the random forest machine learning algorithm. Lastly, we compare the developed maps at 1 km spatial resolution with existing maps generated by Borrelli et al. (2017) i.e. the K_{GloSEM} factor map, which employed soil texture as a proxy for permeability similar to $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor.

2. Methodology

2.1. Input dataset

The primary inputs for generating the global K factor map are the worldwide soil database containing Ksat data and the associated soil and environmental covariates (Fig. 1).

2.2. Global Soil Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity database

The majority of the Global saturated hydraulic conductivity data (81 %) was obtained from Gupta et al. (2021a). The authors compiled a total of 13,258 Ksat values from 100 studies conducted worldwide, which consisted of 4131 values from field measurements and 9155 values from laboratory measurements. Field measurements employed different types

of infiltrometers (e.g., Mini disc infiltrometer, Tension infiltrometer) and permeameters (e.g., Guelph permeameter, Aardvark permeameter), while laboratory analyses predominantly utilized constant or falling head methods. It contains 6532 Ksat values from Florida, USA. To avoid bias resulting from the large number of Florida samples, only 1 % of the Florida samples were utilized, following the approach of Gupta et al. (2021b). The remaining 19 % of the Ksat samples were collected from Martins et al. (2022) and Gonçalves et al. (2013) (please refer to Table 1). The detailed information of methods can be obtained from the respective references. During the data collection for this study, the inclusion criteria required each sample to include information on Ksat, soil texture, and soil organic carbon (SOC). However, some samples lacked SOC information and were supplemented using predicted SOC maps at a spatial resolution of 250 m from SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021). As a result, a total of 5760 samples were ultimately chosen for use in this study from 46 countries (sample locations are depicted in Fig. 2). Due to the scarcity of data from certain regions, we combined estimations of Ksat from various methods, comprising 3251 lab measurements and 2509 field measurements, to create this map. While several studies, such as Mohanty et al. (1994) and Muñoz-Carpena et al. (2002), indicate that there could be significant differences in measurements between lab and field methods, we conducted tests to assess the impact of these differences on the random forest model. The specific indicators used for this

Table 1
Digitized Ksat dataset as number of points on each continent.

Continents	Martins et al. (2022)	Gupta et al. (2021a)	Gonçalves et al. (2013)	Total
North America	–	831	–	831
Europe	–	1826	395	2221
Asia	–	974	–	974
Australia	–	163	–	163
Africa	–	340	–	340
Oceania	–	20	–	20
South America	709	502	–	1211
Total	709	4656	395	5760

assessment are explained in Text S1 and illustrated in Fig. S1.

2.3. Soil and environmental covariates for machine learning

In this study, a total of 25 covariates were utilized, encompassing both soil and environmental factors. The soil covariates consisted of sand and clay content, organic carbon, as well as kaolinite and smectite clay minerals. The global maps for the soil properties were obtained

Fig. 1. Methodology applied to generate the global maps of K factor (K_{wischmeier} factor and K_{ksat} factor).

Fig. 2. The Ksat data locations are depicted in the map, indicating areas with low and high sample density ranging from zero to more than two hundred points at certain locations. The density of points is represented by yellow (low) and purple (high) colors.

from the SoilGrids website (Poggio et al., 2021), while the maps for kaolinite and smectite were obtained from Ito and Wagai (2017). The environmental covariates were divided into four groups: climate, vegetation, topography, and reflectance-based factors. The climate data encompassed various parameters such as annual mean temperature and precipitation, temperature seasonality, maximum temperature during the warmest month, minimum temperature during the coldest month, precipitation during the wettest and driest months, diffuse and direct irradiation, MODIS land surface temperature, and standard deviation of MODIS land surface temperature. Topography consisted of the terrain wetness index, slope, aspect, elevation, and lithology. Surface reflectance involved the reflection of near-infrared (NIR), red, and shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands based on Landsat data. Vegetation included the dataset for the Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR). Table 2 provides a comprehensive list of these covariates, all of which were resampled to 1 km using nearest neighbour method for spatial mapping.

2.4. Estimation of soil erodibility (*K* factor) values

The original *K* factor equation is in $t\ ha\ h\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$ was proposed by Wischmeier and Smith (1978):

$$K = 2.76 \times 10^{-7} M^{1.14} (12 - OM) + 0.0043(s - 2) + 0.0033(p - 3) \quad (1)$$

where *M* represents the textural factor, which is calculated as the product of two components: ($m_{\text{silt}} + m_{\text{vfs}}$) multiplied by $(100 - m_c)$. In this equation, m_c denotes the percentage of clay fraction content, m_{silt} denotes the percentage of silt fraction content, and m_{vfs} denotes the percentage of very fine sand fraction content. Additionally, *OM* is the percentage of organic matter, the soil structure class is represented by *s* (where *s* = 1 corresponds to very fine granular, *s* = 2 to fine granular, *s* = 3 to medium or coarse granular, and *s* = 4 to blocky, platy, or massive), and the permeability class is represented by *p* (where *p* = 1 (>146.4 cm/day) corresponds to very fast, *p* = 2 (48.72–146.4 cm/day) to moderate fast, *p* = 3 (12.24–48.72 cm/day) to moderate, *p* = 4 (4.8–12.24 cm/day) to moderate low, *p* = 5 (2.4–4.8 cm/day) to slow, and *p* = 6 (<2.4 cm/day) to very slow).

Adaptation of the variables in the *K* factor equation was necessary because the equation only applies to regions with a maximum of 4 % organic matter. This limit is related to the fact that agricultural soils are generally characterized by a percentage of organic matter less than or equal to 4 %, and 1352 samples were found to fall into a category with >4 %. Due to the limited data set, we decided not to remove these

samples, but assigned a maximum value of 4 %, as recommended by Efthimiou (2018). Additionally, the equation was not valid for samples with a silt content >70 %. To address this, we used the approach of Panagos et al. (2014) removing samples with over 80 % silt content ($n = 25$) and assigning a maximum value of 70 % for samples with silt content between 70 and 80 % ($n = 300$). Furthermore, many samples lacked very fine sand (VFS) content information, so it was assumed that VFS content accounted for 20 % of the total sand content, as suggested by Panagos et al. (2014). Finally, since there was no information on soil structure, the soil structure classes were assigned based on soil texture classes (see Table 3). There are various studies such as Riquetti et al. (2022) for South America, and Raj et al. (2023) for India using the soil texture information to represent the soil structure classes due to unavailability of the data.

2.5. Permeability class assignment for $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ and K_{Ksat} factor

Permeability classes range from very fast to very slow, indicating the speed at which water infiltrates the soil. As permeability data does not exist on large scales, one possibility is to use soil texture classes to assign the permeability classes (Panagos et al., 2014; Table 4). We followed this path to calculate the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor. However, this pretends that the *K* factor is based on three different parameters, while in the end it is always soil texture information defining these parameter values. Thus, for the K_{Ksat} factor, we determined the permeability class by assigning measured K_{sat} values (Table 4). After computing the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor and K_{Ksat} factor values, we developed the violin plot and bar plot to evaluate the variations in the ranges and changes in the mean values for different continents, respectively, between $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor and K_{Ksat} factor values. Furthermore, we applied the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Berger and Zhou, 2014) to check the normality of the distribution and found that the datasets for both $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor and K_{Ksat} are non-normally distributed. Therefore, we used the Kruskal-Wallis test (McKight and Najab, 2010) to assess the significant difference between the two datasets. We then linked the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor and K_{Ksat} factor values with soil and environmental covariates to produce two global maps: the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor map and the K_{Ksat} factor map.

2.6. *K* factor mapping using machine learning algorithm

The quantile random forest algorithm was utilized to map the K_{Ksat} factor and $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor values. This was done by superimposing the estimated *K* factor values locations on environmental covariates, and then extracting the values at each location to form a regression matrix

Table 2
List of covariates used for creating the K factor map at 1 km.

S. no	List of covariates	Units	Source
<i>Climate</i>			
1	Annual mean temperature	°C	http://chelsea-climate.org/bioc
2	Temperature seasonality	°C	lim/ (Karger et al., 2017)
3	Maximum temperature of warmest month	°C	
4	Minimum temperature of coldest month	°C	
5	Annual mean precipitation	mm	
6	Precipitation of wettest month	mm	
7	Precipitation of driest month	mm	
8	Diffuse irradiation	kWh/m ²	https://globalsolaratlas.info/download/world
9	Direct irradiation	kWh/m ²	
10	MODIS land surface temperature	K	https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mod11a2v006/
11	Standard deviation of MODIS land surface temperature	K	
<i>Digital terrain model</i>			
12	Terrain wetness index	–	https://zenodo.org/record/1447210#.XilTejFKhaQ (Yamazaki et al., 2017)
13	Slope	%	
14	Aspect	degrees	
15	Elevation	m	
16	Lithology	–	
<i>Surface reflectance</i>			
17	Landsat NIR band	–	Hansen et al. (2013)
18	Landsat Red band	–	
19	Landsat SWIR band	–	
<i>Vegetation covariates</i>			
20	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation	–	https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/fapar
<i>Predicted soil properties</i>			
21	Sand content (0–30 cm)	%	Poggio et al. (2021)
22	Clay content (0–30 cm)	%	
23	Soil organic carbon content (0–30 cm)	%	
24	Kaolinite clay mineral	%	Ito and Wagai (2017)
25	Smectite clay mineral	%	

Table 3
Assignment of soil structure classes based on soil texture classes proposed by Bagarello et al. (2009).

Structure class	Soil texture
1 (very fine granular)	Sandy, loamy sand, and sandy loam
2 (finer granular)	Sandy clay, sandy clay loam, silt loam and silt
3 (medium or coarse granular)	Clay loam and silty clay loam
4 (blocky, platy, or massive)	Clay and silty clay

using the ‘terra’ package in R. Prior to applying the final model, the best hyper-parameters of the model were determined. The optimal mtry (number of variables randomly selected as candidates at each split) was estimated using a five-fold spatial cross-validation method, while default values were employed for other hyper-parameters (i.e., tree number of 500 and a final node size of 5 points). The spatial cross-validation procedure was conducted in accordance with the Gupta et al. (2021b) protocol, which entailed dividing the global map into 1-degree by 1-degree blocks and splitting the grids into five subsets, each containing 20 % of the data. The QRF model was applied five times,

Table 4
Permeability classes defined based on texture class ($K_{Wischmeier}$) and K_{ksat} proposed by Panagos et al. (2014). They assigned these classes based on US Department of Agriculture's National Soils Handbook No. 430 (USDA, 1983).

Permeability class	Soil texture (to define $K_{Wischmeier}$)	Saturated hydraulic conductivity (cm/day) (to define K_{ksat})
1 (fast and very fast)	Sand	>146.4
2 (moderate fast)	Loamy sand, sandy loam	48.72–146.4
3 (moderate)	Loam, silty loam	12.24–48.72
4 (moderate low)	Sandy clay loam, clay loam	4.8–12.24
5 (slow)	Silty clay loam, sand clay	2.4–4.8
6 (very slow)	Silty clay, clay	<2.4

with a different subset being excluded each time for model validation. The predictions for all subsets were then combined and compared to the measured values to compute accuracy metrics. This process was repeated for all mtry values ranging from 1 to 25, and the optimal values with low Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) were selected. The final mtry value was then used to fit the final model and to estimate the accuracy of the model. The accuracy of the models was estimated using Coefficient of determination (R^2) and RMSE. Using the residual sum of squares (RSS) metrics (Gupta et al., 2021b), we estimated the relative importance of each variable. To rank the importance of the covariates, we considered the highest decrease in RSS as the most significant covariate. We used quantile regression (QR) to calculate the uncertainty, which is a post-processing technique that generates uncertainty estimates based on model residues (i.e., the differences between observed and predicted data). The QR function can calculate any quantile (Kasraei et al., 2021). Detailed information about the methodology can be found in Rahmati et al. (2019) and Kasraei et al. (2021). We computed the 90 % prediction intervals (PI) by calculating the quantiles at 0.05 and 0.95 using the quantreg option in the R package ‘ranger’ (Wright and Ziegler, 2015).

2.7. Comparison between K_{ksat} , $K_{Wischmeier}$, and K_{GloSEM} factor

In this study, the K_{ksat} factor map was compared to the K_{GloSEM} factor map and $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor map. For the K_{GloSEM} factor map (Borelli et al., 2017, Eq. (1)) the permeability classes were also based on soil texture but soil properties (SOC and soil texture) was drawn from the SoilGrids map (Hengl et al., 2017). Note that the methodologies of K_{GloSEM} factor and $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor are quite similar, with the main distinction that K_{GloSEM} factor utilized direct predicted soil properties maps to estimate the K factor, while $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor first estimated it based on measured soil properties and then linked it with different covariates to create a map. Furthermore, to test the statistical differences in predicted values among K_{ksat} , $K_{Wischmeier}$, and K_{GloSEM} across different continents, climates, lithologies, and World Reference Base (WRB) classes, we selected the Kruskal-Wallis test. We chose this test because the predicted data are non-normally distributed, as determined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

2.8. Verification

To verify the accuracy of K_{ksat} and $K_{Wischmeier}$, we collected the mean values from reference studies. We specifically chose studies conducted on a national or continental scale. In total, 13 studies were compared with K_{ksat} and $K_{Wischmeier}$, and the differences between their mean values were estimated. The authors made efforts to maximize the representativeness of the global context, however, it is important to note that the majority of the studies were conducted at the local and regional scales.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Statistical characteristics of K factor values

The violin plots in Fig. 3 depicted K_{Ksat} factor and $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor for the 5760 samples. K_{Ksat} factor exhibited a wider range than $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor with simultaneously having a lower mean value of K_{Ksat} factor ($0.023 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$) compared to $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor ($0.027 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$), however significantly different. Major differences in the K_{Ksat} factor and the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor were observed in Tropical regions (South America and Africa) while both values were relatively similar in temperate regions (North America, Europe, and Asia, Fig. 4a and b). Comparing the K_{Ksat} factor to the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor resulted in a 40 % decrease in South America followed by 25 %, 23 %, 22 %, 12 %, 8 %, and 5 % decrease in Australia, Africa, Oceania, Asia, North America, and Europe, respectively. The smaller differences observed in Asia, North America, and Europe mirrors that the equation was developed based on temperate soils or samples from the United States (Bagarello et al., 2012), which results in soil texture classes roughly representing the Ksat values in these regions. However, the equation is less suitable for tropical soils, as these regions contain soils like, e.g. ferrosols with high clay and iron content. Consequently, a change of 40 % and 23 % was observed in the tropical regions.

3.2. Random forest model accuracy and covariates importance

The model for the K_{Ksat} factor had an R^2 value of 0.93, while the model for the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor had an R^2 value of 0.98. To evaluate the importance of the covariates, residual sum of squares (RSS) metrics were utilized, revealing that the most critical covariate was sand content, followed by clay content and precipitation of the wettest month (Fig. 5). For the $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ factor, sand content was the most influential factor. The findings align with the studies conducted by Ostovari et al. (2022) and Bonilla and Johnson (2012), which also identified a strong correlation between mean K factor and sand content. However, by incorporating

Ksat (K_{Ksat} factor), the significance of clay content and other covariates increased (Fig. 5). This increase in the importance of clay content might be reflecting the properties of different clay minerals (kaolinite and smectite) through measured Ksat values. On the other hand, organic carbon exhibits a weak correlation with soil erodibility. Previous research has also yielded similar results, indicating that organic matter alone does not explain the erodibility of soils. This is because organic matter interacts with other factors, such as texture and permeability (Jin et al., 2009; Tejada and Gonzalez, 2006). It may also suggest that proxies used for organic carbon, such as assuming that >4 % organic matter is equal to 4 % and using predicted organic carbon values, do not significantly impact soil erodibility values.

3.3. Spatial distribution of K (K_{Ksat}) factor map

The K_{Ksat} factor map (Fig. 6a) reveals that tropical climate regions, particularly parts of South America and Africa, exhibit lower values compared to temperate and other climatic regions. This difference in values might be due to the presence of Oxisols (USDA soil taxonomy) or Ferralsols (world reference base major soil group). These soils are highly weathered, resulting in clayey tropical soils (mainly kaolinite and some iron oxides such as hematite and goethite) that are strongly flocculated and exhibiting pseudo-sand behavior. This behavior enhanced infiltration and exhibiting pseudo-sand behavior. This behavior enhanced infiltration (El-Swaify, 1980; Sanchez, 1976). The mean K_{Ksat} values were estimated for different world reference soil types (Fig. S3 and Table 5). The minimum value of K_{Ksat} factor was noticed in Ferrasols and other major soil types found in tropical regions. de Faria Godoi et al. (2021) developed a soil erodibility map for Brazil and observed also the minimum value of soil erodibility in Ferrasols compared to other soil types. However, a few regions in South America also display higher K factor values relative to other regions in South America. Parts of Uruguay and Argentina also exhibit higher K factor values due to soil compaction caused by domestic animals, which affects the soil's hydraulic properties (Horton et al., 1994; Castillo et al., 2021). China's North plain exhibits notably high values of the K factor, which might be attributed to high agricultural activities (Yin et al., 2016). Additionally, over time, most land-use types remained stable in this region, except for the conversion of cropland to built-up areas during the period of 2000–2015, which could also be a contributing factor (Yu and Deng, 2022). Furthermore, we observed relatively high K factor values in the Loess Plateau (Han et al., 2023), as well as in the northeast of China, where typical black soil (Chernozem) predominates. The high values of the K factor might be due to large-scale vegetation destruction caused by human activity, intense rainfall during summer, strong winds in winter and spring, as well as freezing and thawing in the northeast of China (Mackenzie et al., 2018; Fan, 2004). Conversely, the southern central and south coast of China have relatively lower K factor values due to the presence of ultisols/acrisols and oxisols/ferrosols (USDA soil taxonomy/WRB), which are highly weathered soils (Zhang et al., 2008), which can be assumed to have higher infiltration capacity.

In central India, the relatively lower values of K_{Ksat} can be attributed to the high content of smectite clay, which reduces soil detachment (Meyer and Harmon, 1984). However, the detachment can vary depending on rainfall intensity. In contrast, the Indo-Gangetic plain exhibits high values of K_{Ksat} due to its predominance of agricultural land use, higher bulk density, poor water retention (especially in sandy loam soils), lower organic carbon content, and reduced biological activities (Singh et al., 2016). These factors can increase soil susceptibility towards erosion. Northern European countries such as Norway, Finland, and Sweden demonstrate comparatively lower values primarily because of their high organic carbon content, while countries like France, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Germany exhibit relatively higher values, which can be attributed to the presence of the Loess belt, lower levels of organic carbon, and high percentage of silt content (Ballabio et al., 2016; de Brogniez et al., 2015; Panagos et al., 2014).

The erodibility patterns observed in Poland resemble the erodibility

Fig. 3. The distribution of K factor values is depicted in the violin plot. The super script alphabetical letters show the significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between $K_{\text{Wischmeier}}$ and K_{Ksat} factors. Note that by including measured Ksat values (K_{Ksat}), the mean K factor values decreased in comparison to those obtained through soil texture-based permeability values.

Fig. 4. a) The mean K factor values for various continents are displayed based on K_{sat} (red color) and soil texture ($K_{Wischmeier}$, cyan color). b) The percentage change between the K_{sat} and $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor values among different continents. The greatest difference is observed in the tropical regions (Africa and South America) compared to the temperate regions (North America, Europe, and Asia).

Fig. 5. The relative importance of the covariates utilized in the QRF model for the two different K factors, as the average increase in node purity. The larger the value, the more significant the covariate. The top 10 most important covariates for K factor are presented for cases involving a) K_{Ksat} factor and b) $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor. MTCM, PWM, AAR, TS, LST_SD, DI, and TWI represent the minimum temperature of the coldest month, precipitation of the wettest month, Average annual rainfall, temperature seasonality, standard deviation of land surface temperature, direct irradiation, and terrain wetness index, respectively.

map provided by Marcinkowski et al. (2022), indicating lower values in North Poland and higher values in South Poland. Regarding North America, Florida has low K factor values due to its high sand content, which facilitates greater infiltration. Conversely, parts of Texas and the Midwest region of the United States illustrate relatively high values, likely due to extensive cultivation of agricultural cropland and intensive soil tillage practices, resulting in lower organic carbon levels (Ratta and Lal, 1998).

3.4. Comparison between K_{Ksat} factor, $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor, and K_{GloSEM} factor

When comparing the K_{Ksat} with $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor map (Fig. 6), K_{Ksat} factor values are lower in tropical regions but a relatively small difference in other climate regions (as seen in the Table 5 and Fig. S2a). In

South America, the average $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor value was noticed to be $0.022 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ (Table 5). This is congruent with Riquetti et al. (2022), who established permeability classes based on soil texture classes. However, upon integrating the measured K_{sat} in K_{Ksat} factor, the mean value for south America decreased to $0.018 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$. Raj et al. (2023) developed the soil erodibility map for India and computed the mean value of $0.028 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$, which is based on a similar approach as Riquetti et al. (2022) and approximately aligns with the $K_{Wischmeier}$ mean value ($0.027 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$) for India. However, after incorporating the K_{sat} values, the mean values again decreased to $0.024 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$. These lower K_{Ksat} compared to soil texture-based K factors may indicate that neglecting the hydraulic properties in the calculation results in an overestimation of the K value. The change in the mean value for North America between $K_{Wischmeier}$ and K_{Ksat} factor was minimal. Similarly, the mean value of

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of the global K factor maps ($\text{t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$). a) K_{ksat} factor, b) $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor, and c) K_{GloSEM} factor. d) The probability distribution function illustrates the broader range of K_{ksat} factor map.

K_{ksat} factor for Europe resembled the value of $0.027 \text{ t ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$ estimated by Panagos et al. (2014), after accounting for the surface stone cover. Relating the K_{ksat} factor values to lithology indicate lower values in metamorphic rocks, acid plutonic rocks, and unconsolidated sediment compared to the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor, as shown in Table 5. This particular type of parent material is commonly found in tropical regions, as depicted in the Global Lithological Map (GLiM) lithological classes (Fig. S4). A study conducted by Moosdorf et al. (2018) also computed the global erodibility index, which represents the potential for sediment production in different rock types. They observed a low erodibility index for metamorphic rocks and acid plutonic rocks, but a high erodibility index for unconsolidated sediment. In our own analysis, we found that regions with significant amounts of unconsolidated sediment, such as India, USA, Russia, and China, exhibited higher soil erodibility indices. Conversely, regions like South America, Africa, and Australia displayed lower soil erodibility values (Please note that the Sahara Desert region is excluded from the mean values).

Compared to the K_{GloSEM} factor map (Fig. 6c), the K_{ksat} factor map demonstrates increased variability, revealing distinct erodibility values across different climatic regions. In tropical regions, low K_{ksat} factor values are observed, while temperate regions exhibit high values. However, there are also several regions within the temperate climate that display relatively high K_{ksat} factor values compared to K_{GloSEM} factor. For example, Argentina, South Africa, the western part of

Australia, parts of West and Northeast China, a part of the Midwest USA, and Western Europe (refer to Fig. S2b, for possible reasons see above). The difference between the two maps might partly also due to the utilization of latest version of soil properties data for the K_{ksat} . It is worth noting that the K_{GloSEM} factor map was developed based on the first version of SoilGrids (Hengl et al., 2017), which employed less data compared to SoilGrids 2.0 (Poggio et al., 2021) used in this study. Furthermore, in contrast to both the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor and K_{GloSEM} factor maps, the K_{ksat} factor map exhibits an evenly spread-out distribution (see Fig. 6d). This might be related to the regions that are modified after incorporating the Ksat values.

3.5. Uncertainty of K factor maps

A 90 % prediction interval is used to indicate uncertainties, with the 5th and 95th percentiles. Pixels with higher values have greater uncertainties. The K_{ksat} factor (Fig. 7a) had lower uncertainties than the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor (Fig. 7b) in most regions, especially in tropical climate regions where a significant difference was observed. In general, higher uncertainties are noticed in parts of Russia, which is most likely due to the sparse available Ksat data, a major source of error in digital soil mapping (Malone et al., 2018). There are also other regions with high uncertainties, such as the Mid-west USA and the northern part of China. The high uncertainties in these regions might be due to errors associated

Table 5

The mean values of continent, climate zones, lithology units, world reference soil types specific soil erodibility values in $t\ ha\ h^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$. The super script alphabetical letters show the significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between $K_{Wischmeier}$, K_{ksat} , and K_{GloSEM} factors.

	$K_{Wischmeier}$ factor	K_{ksat} factor	K_{GloSEM} factor
<i>Continents</i>			
North America	0.028 ^a	0.027 ^b	0.028 ^c
Europe	0.028 ^a	0.027 ^b	0.027 ^c
Asia	0.030 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.031 ^c
Australia	0.018 ^a	0.015 ^b	0.018 ^c
Africa	0.019 ^a	0.015 ^b	0.019 ^c
Oceania	0.023 ^a	0.019 ^b	0.021 ^c
South America	0.022 ^a	0.018 ^b	0.019 ^c
<i>Climatic zones</i>			
Temperate	0.027 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.025 ^c
Tropical	0.022 ^a	0.017 ^b	0.021 ^c
Boreal	0.030 ^a	0.030 ^b	0.031 ^c
Arid	0.023 ^a	0.021 ^b	0.025 ^c
Polar	0.029 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.028 ^c
<i>Lithology units</i>			
Acid plutonic rocks	0.025 ^a	0.023 ^b	0.026 ^c
Acid volcanic rocks	0.026 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.027 ^c
Basic plutonic rocks	0.030 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.030 ^c
Basic volcanic rocks	0.029 ^a	0.027 ^b	0.029 ^c
Carbonate sedimentary rocks	0.029 ^a	0.028 ^b	0.029 ^c
Evaporites	0.023 ^a	0.021 ^a	0.025 ^b
Intermediate plutonic rocks	0.026 ^a	0.024 ^b	0.027 ^c
Intermediate volcanic rocks	0.029 ^a	0.027 ^b	0.029 ^c
Metamorphic rocks	0.023 ^a	0.021 ^b	0.024 ^c
Mixed sedimentary rocks	0.029 ^a	0.028 ^b	0.030 ^c
Pyroclastics	0.028 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.027 ^c
Siliciclastic sedimentary rocks	0.027 ^a	0.026 ^b	0.027 ^c
Unconsolidated sediments	0.024 ^a	0.022 ^b	0.024 ^c
<i>World reference soil groups</i>			
Acrisols	0.025 ^a	0.021 ^b	0.023 ^c
Andosols	0.027 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.030 ^c
Arenosols	0.017 ^a	0.015 ^b	0.016 ^c
Cambisols	0.030 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.030 ^c
Chernozems	0.031 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.030 ^c
Ferralsols	0.021 ^a	0.015 ^b	0.019 ^c
Fluvisols	0.027 ^a	0.026 ^b	0.027 ^c
Gleysols	0.031 ^a	0.031 ^b	0.030 ^c
Greyzems	0.032 ^a	0.032 ^b	0.033 ^c
Histosols	0.029 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.027 ^c
Kastanozems	0.029 ^a	0.028 ^b	0.031 ^c
Lithosols	0.029 ^a	0.028 ^b	0.029 ^c
Luvissols	0.025 ^a	0.023 ^b	0.025 ^c
Nitisols	0.023 ^a	0.017 ^b	0.020 ^c
Phaeozems	0.031 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.029 ^c
Planosols	0.023 ^a	0.021 ^b	0.025 ^c
Podzols	0.025 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.026 ^c
Podzoluvissols	0.028 ^a	0.029 ^b	0.031 ^c
Rankers	0.026 ^a	0.025 ^a	0.020 ^b
Regosols	0.026 ^a	0.025 ^b	0.026 ^c
Rendzinas	0.027 ^a	0.024 ^b	0.025 ^c
Solonchaks	0.025 ^a	0.024 ^b	0.031 ^c
Solonetz	0.025 ^a	0.024 ^b	0.027 ^c
Vertisols	0.026 ^a	0.022 ^b	0.023 ^c
Xerosols	0.024 ^a	0.023 ^b	0.028 ^c
Yermosols	0.022 ^a	0.021 ^b	0.027 ^c

with Ksat sampling methods and positional accuracy (Gomes et al., 2019) as the Ksat dataset used in the study is based on different methods of measurements and also contains some samples with lower positional accuracy.

3.6. Impact of Ksat on soil erodibility

The incorporation of Ksat values led to a decrease in the K factor values in Europe, South America, Australia, and Africa continents. With

a decrease in K factor, soil erosion decreases. Panagos et al. (2014) considered the stone cover and which led to a decrease in the K factor. They argued that neglecting this effect resulted in an overestimation of soil erosion. Likewise, a recent global study conducted by Yang et al. (2023), which aimed to generate a soil erodibility map with surface stone cover, also demonstrated a reduction in soil erodibility. However, the values proposed by Yang et al. (2023) were higher compared to the findings of Panagos et al. (2014). The consideration of the Ksat into the K_{ksat} led to a greater reduction in soil erodibility compared to the maps including stone cover (Panagos et al., 2014) (Fig. 8). Likewise, de Faria Godoi et al. (2021) developed the soil erodibility map for Brazil, with a mean value of $0.018\ t\ ha\ h^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$. The latter study noted an overestimation of predicted soil erodibility in comparison to measured values (de Faria Godoi et al., 2021). After incorporating the Ksat values in this study, the mean K_{ksat} value reduced to $0.016\ t\ ha\ h^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$. We would like to point out that Ksat not only includes the effect of stone cover but also encompasses the impact of vegetation roots and other potential macro pores, which can enhance infiltration and increase Ksat by a factor of 1–4.23 (Wang et al., 2020), as well as reduce soil erodibility.

Generally, the influence of Ksat on the K factor is more significant in Southern regions compared to Northern regions with smaller differences between K_{ksat} and the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor in Northern regions compared to Southern regions (Table 5). The Wischmeier equation was originally developed for North America and applied and adapted multiple times for Europe. Including the Ksat information might be considered at the next crucial step to improve the K factor for regions where the Wischmeier equation has not been tested. Further research is needed in different continents (Southern) and climatic regions (Tropical) to further refine (and eventually validate) the K factor.

3.7. Comparison of K-factor estimates to national and continental scales

Many researchers have developed soil erodibility maps at national and continental scales. In Table 6, we included several studies and compared the mean values of K_{ksat} and $K_{Wischmeier}$ with the mean values of these studies and estimated the percentage change. Notably, some studies, such as Wang et al. (2016), de Faria Godoi et al. (2021), Riquetti et al. (2022) etc. validated their maps using measured data and demonstrated good agreement. Therefore, it is worthwhile to compare the map values with the K_{ksat} and $K_{Wischmeier}$ map values. It is important to note that these studies did not consider the measured Ksat in their research. The table indicates that the K_{ksat} factor for all countries, except Slovakia, Poland, and Greece, has a negative value, implying lower K factor values compared to the reference studies. The change between K_{ksat} and K reference ranges from 7.6 % to a substantial decrease of approximately 60 % in Lithuania.

The mean deviation between K_{ksat} and $K_{reference}$ is 13.1 %, while the deviations between both the $K_{Wischmeier}$ map and $K_{reference}$, and the K_{GloSEM} map and $K_{reference}$, are 7.2 %, respectively. These results demonstrate good agreement with the reference studies. The lower K_{ksat} values may represent the effects of including Ksat information. In the case of the maps by de Faria Godoi et al. (2021), upon comparison with measured values, they observed an overestimation. Specifically, for the K_{ksat} factor, the values decreased even further to 0.016, potentially indicating a reduction in the error. A similar overestimation case was also noticed in the studies by Riquetti et al. (2022) and Wang et al. (2016). This observation might suggest that neglecting Ksat and relying on proxies such as soil texture classes contributed to the overestimation of soil erodibility.

3.8. Limitation and future work

In many regions, such as Russia, Canada, Western Australia, and Southern Africa, as well as nearly all of Scandinavia, data are very limited, highlighting the need for additional sample collection to reduce

Fig. 7. Uncertainty map of a) K_{ksat} factor b) $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor. The Quantile regression was used to estimate the 5 and 95 % quantiles. The unit of K factor is $t\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$.

Fig. 8. The comparison between European maps of a) K_{ksat} factor b) K factor including stoniness (Panagos et al., 2014) c) K factor without stoniness (Panagos et al., 2014). The unit of K factor is $t\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$.

uncertainty in these areas. This limitation could also constrain the use of a 1 km spatial resolution for the soil erodibility map, as some regions lack a single sample to adequately represent them. In such cases, the use

of uncertainty maps is highly recommended. Furthermore, obtaining climate data at a higher resolution would contribute to further improving the spatial accuracy of the maps.

Table 6

Comparison of K-factor estimates with National and continental scale studies. The sign (–) is applied in case the aggregated $K_{ksat} / K_{Wischmeier}$ factor data are lower than the ones found in the literature ($K_{reference}$). The unit of K factor is $t\ ha\ ha^{-1}\ MJ^{-1}\ mm^{-1}$.

	Reference	$K_{reference}$ factor	K_{ksat} factor (this study)	$K_{Wischmeier}$ factor	K_{GloSEM} factor	K_{ksat} factor deviation (%)	$K_{Wischmeier}$ factor deviation (%)	K_{GloSEM} factor deviation (%)
Hungary	Centeri and Pataki (2000)	0.0293	0.026	0.026	0.029	(–) 12.6	(–) 12.6	(–) 1.03
Slovakia	Styk et al. (2008)	0.029	0.030	0.031	0.029	3.3	6.4	0
Czech Republic	Dostal et al. (2002)	0.0376	0.032	0.033	0.027	(–) 17.5	(–) 13.9	(–) 39.25
Lithuania	Mazvila et al. (2010)	0.035	0.022	0.021	0.027	(–) 59.1	(–) 66.6	(–) 29.6
Poland	Marcinkowski et al. (2022)	0.016	0.021	0.020	0.025	23.8	20	36
India	Raj et al. (2023)	0.028	0.024	0.027	0.027	(–) 16.6	(–) 3.7	(–) 3.7
Brazil	de Faria Godoi et al. (2021)	0.018	0.016	0.022	0.020	(–) 12.5	18.1	10.0
South America	Riquetti et al. (2022)	0.022	0.018	0.021	0.020	(–) 22.5	(–) 4.7	(–) 10.0
Greece	Efthimiou (2020)	0.024	0.026	0.027	0.028	7.6	11.1	14.2
Switzerland	Schmidt et al. (2018)	0.0327	0.029	0.030	0.027	(–) 12.7	(–) 9.0	(–) 21.1
China	Wang et al. (2016)	0.0321	0.027	0.029	0.029	(–) 18.8	(–) 10.6	(–) 10.6
China	Teng et al. (2019)	0.0320	0.027	0.029	0.029	(–) 18.5	(–) 10.3	(–) 10.3
Europe	Panagos et al. (2014)	0.032	0.027	0.027	0.026	(–) 18.5	(–) 18.5	(–) 23.07
Overall average		0.0282	0.025	0.0263	0.0263	– (13.1)	(–) 7.2	(–) 7.2

Currently, the soil structure classes are based on soil texture classes due to the unavailability of the required dataset. Incorporating soil structure information has the potential to enhance the accuracy of K factor estimates. However, it's worth noting that soil structure can also be approximated by Ksat values (Eck et al., 2016). As mentioned in the methodology section, the equation is valid for organic matter (OM) equal to or <4 %, and approximately 22 % of the samples have >4 % OM, for which predicted OC values are used. This may have some impact on forest soils; however, it appears not to be significant, as indicated in Fig. 5, where OC is not sensitive to calculating soil erodibility. Bonilla and Johnson (2012) employed two equations, Wischmeier and Smith (1978) for <4 % OM and Römken et al. (1977) for >4 % OM. Following their analysis, they concluded that the entire dataset (including both greater and <4 % OM) did not exhibit a significant correlation with organic carbon. There was also no correlation observed between OC samples with <4 % OM and soil erodibility. Moreover, as mentioned in the methods section, due to data limitations, we combined laboratory and field methods for Ksat data, which could introduce uncertainties into the model's accuracy. However, excluding either field or lab-measured data from the analysis would leave many regions unrepresented (see Fig. S5). Therefore, we tested the impact of combining Ksat methods on the random forest model. The results indicate that this factor emerged as the least important, suggesting that merging these samples in this study is a viable approach (Fig. S1).

Further, the modified maps need to be validated in selected catchments with measured sediment yield datasets in order to evaluate their reliability and accuracy. However, our aim here is to make the first step towards a further significant contribution to the assessment of global soil erosion (GSER) led by a group of 50 soil erosion experts in partnership with the Global Soil Partnership (GSP) - Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soils (ITPS) (FAO). The aim of this partnership is to develop a standardized technical manual for globally harmonized mapping of soil erosion. We believe that soil erodibility is a crucial factor in estimating soil erosion and can provide valuable input for the (GSER) assessment. Furthermore, we expanded the Ksat dataset distribution across globe with the help of ESDAC in order to enhance the accuracy of this map. The new version can be expected in next 3–4 years.

4. Conclusion

We propose a new global soil erodibility (K) factor map, called the K_{ksat} factor map, which is considering the saturated hydraulic

conductivity (Ksat) as an independent parameter next to soil texture. Previous soil erodibility maps, developed at various scales ranging from local to global, basically considered soil texture, as the other two parameters, soil structure as well as permeability classes are also based on soil texture data. We incorporated measured Ksat values obtained from existing published data bases into the permeability class of the Wischmeier and Smith (1978) equation.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the K_{ksat} factor, we compared it with the $K_{Wischmeier}$ factor and K_{GloSEM} factor maps. We used the random forest machine learning algorithm to establish a relationship between each of the K factor values and various soil and environmental factors to generate maps with a spatial resolution of 1 km, along with corresponding uncertainty maps. We noted a general decrease in Kksat compared to $K_{Wischmeier}$ and K_{GloSEM} which might at least partly address the frequently observed overestimation of (R)USLE modeled erosion rates compared to measured values. K_{ksat} is different in tropical regions, likely reflecting the difference in soil properties (e.g., clay and iron) and that the original K factor was developed for temperate regions. We also inferred that Ksat serves not only as an indicator for the presence of stone cover, but also encompasses the influence of vegetation roots or other potential macro pores, which enhance infiltration and subsequently reduce soil erodibility.

This study represents the first step in integrating hydraulic properties into the K factor of USLE-type models taking the importance of hydrological processes for soil erosion strength into account. Immediate further research need would be improvement in K_{ksat} maps by incorporating additional distributed Ksat values especially in regions with scarce data (Russia, Canada, Western Australia, Southern Africa, nearly all of Scandinavia) to ensure a better representation of soil structure and hydraulic properties in these regions. As Ksat is a dynamic property that often changes with alterations in land use and land cover, a dynamic data set might also be a worthy aim of future research.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Surya Gupta: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Pasquale Borrelli:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Panos Panagos:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Christine Alewell:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article text or are freely available at the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC, <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>), the institutional soil data repository of the European Commission Joint Research Centre (Panagos et al., 2022). The code for preparing the data and the map is available at <https://github.com/ETHZ-repositories/Soil-erodibility-mapping>.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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